

THE ROLE OF BIOLOGY AND PHYSICS IN THE SYSTEM OF MEDICAL EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6502308>

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Abstract: *Physics, biology and medicine are closely related sciences: many of the most important discoveries in the field of physics were made by physicians - a fact that at first glance seems rather unusual. For example, in the 40s. 19th century Yu. R. Mayer, being a ship's doctor, while sailing in the tropics, discovered a difference in the color of venous blood between residents of countries with hot and cold climates.*

Key words: *physics, biology, medicine, science*

It is necessary for a future doctor to know physics, since reliance on physical laws allows studying the functioning of a living organism, explaining normal physiological and pathological processes. Despite the complexity and interconnection of various processes in the human body, many of them are close to physical ones.

Blood circulation is a process associated with the work of the heart (mechanics), the generation of bio potentials (electricity), the flow of fluid (hydrodynamics), the propagation of elastic vibrations through the vessels (oscillations and waves). Respiration is associated with heat transfer (thermodynamics), evaporation (phase transformations).

In addition, in the body, in addition to physical macro processes, molecular processes occur that ultimately determine the behavior of biological systems. Understanding the physics of these micro processes is necessary for a correct assessment of the state of the body, the nature of a number of diseases, and the effects (including side effects) of drugs. Some physical concepts are basic for understanding the structure and functioning of the human body. For example, from the standpoint of the general laws of mechanics, the musculoskeletal system is a system of levers: the hip joint is a type I lever, the ankle joint is a type II lever, and the forearm is a type III lever. The even position of the head (the atlantooccipital articulation is also a lever of the first kind) is due to the equality of the moments of gravity applied to the center of gravity of the skull and the force of muscle traction. A change in any of these forces leads to a change in the position of the head.

Levers are also widely used in medical instruments: scissors of various types, forceps, wire cutters, etc. Some manipulations performed by a doctor also have a lever

implementation (a dentist uses the law of conservation of moment of force when extracting a tooth).

Many diagnostic and treatment methods are based on the use of physical principles: the operation of a medical thermometer is based on the thermal expansion of mercury, the device of a stethoscope (phonendoscope) used in auscultation is based on the properties of vibrations and waves.

That is why in the process of teaching students physics in a medical school, it is necessary to cover sections directly related to medicine. An important role in the educational process is played by modern multimedia technologies. Demonstration devices used in lectures and practical classes allow improving the learning process and familiarizing future physicians in detail with the physical methods used in modern medical diagnostics and treatment.

In the system of medical education, the study of biology is determined by the fact that biology is the theoretical basis of medicine. Since a person is a part of wildlife, the laws of the structure and functioning of living organisms apply to the processes of human life in normal and pathological conditions.

"Medicine, taken in terms of theory, is, first of all, general biology," wrote one of the greatest theoreticians of medicine. All medical sciences use fundamental knowledge about the general biological patterns of human development, structure and life.

Advances in medicine are closely related to biological research, so the doctor must be aware of the latest advances in modern biology. It suffices to give a few examples from the history of science to show the close connection between the successes of medicine and the discoveries made in the field of biology.

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